

57th CIRP Conference on Manufacturing Systems 2024 (CMS 2024)

Laser Metal Deposition Based Embedding of Optical Fibers

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Abstract

Laser metal deposition (LMD) is generative manufacturing that allows fabrication on existing metal parts with five axes, utilizing different metal powders independent of the substrate metal. LMD provides convenience to embed sensor closely underneath functional surfaces. The optical fiber is flexible and multifunctional, well suited to be used as a sensor and embedded beneath metal for measuring parameters such as temperature and strain. However, in order to maintain the functionality of optical fiber after welding, it is crucial to choose right deposition parameters for LMD. The parameters of LMD may vary for different metals and finding appropriate parameters require iterations and optimizations. Also, necessary shielding techniques are required to protect the fiber from heat. This paper identifies optimized parameters for LMD taking into account the surface quality of functional surface and the heat impact while upholding the fibers. Further, optimized parameters are applied to embed the optical fiber. Further, the heat impact of welding is inspected visually and through microcomputed tomography (Micro-CT) scans. Achieved results are compared with the previous experiment. Results show that the identified optimized parameters of LMD are relevant for welding optical fiber inside metal. No heat impact on core fiber is evident thus preserving its functionality. Improvement of surface quality and effects of LMD on optical characteristics of the fibers is proposed in future work.

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Peer-review under responsibility of the scientific committee of the 57th CIRP Conference on Manufacturing Systems 2024 (CMS 2024)

Keywords: laser metal deposition (LMD); optical fiber; sensor embedding; smart sensing

1. Introduction

Optical fibers (OF) are capable to measure temperature, strain, and stress with high accuracy and maximum reliability [1]. They are passive, resistant to electromagnetic interference, environmental resilient, integrable to harsh environments and comprise multifunctional sensing capability [2]. Since the optical fiber sensors (OFS) are light weight and flexible, they are easily embeddable into various structures near functional surfaces. The optical fiber sensors are widely used in automobile, manufacturing, bio-medical, chemical, oil and gas industry [3].

Laser metal deposition (LMD) is categorized as directed energy deposition (DED) technique of additive manufacturing through which entire part or component is manufactured layer by layer [4]. The capability of LMD to fabricate on existing

parts with five-axis is advantageous [5]. Through LMD, two metals can be welded together, surface can be improved by metal coating, and new tools can be manufactured [4,6]. LMD is proved to be an enabling technology to embed optical fiber in sheet metal beneath functional surfaces [7]. The applications may include aerospace, automotive, manufacturing, and structural engineering, where it is crucial to monitor and analyze the behavior of metal components under different operating conditions in real time with non-intrusive means of gathering data [8–10].

Since high temperature and stresses are involved in LMD [11], embedding of optical fiber beneath functional surfaces in metallic components may present a significant challenge. In order to minimize the heat impact and avoid damaging optical fiber, it is essential to derive protective mechanisms for optical fiber sensors and find suitable LMD process parameters for

successful embedding of fiber inside metal near functional surfaces.

The primary objective of this work is to identify optimized parameters for LMD in order to minimize heat impact of embedding fiber optical cable beneath metal surfaces. The identified optimized parameters are then applied to a sheet metal part to embed optical fibers beneath the functional surface while (i) preserving light propagating properties of the fibers and (ii) maintaining the surface quality of the printed part. The attained outcomes are being compared to those of the prior experiment. This novel work may provide future researchers exemplary process parameters for LMD to embed optical sensors inside existing tools.

The overall structure of this research paper is as follows: Section 2 summarizes current state of the art in the field and highlights the research gap. Then, proposed methodology to optimize parameters for embedding optical fiber with LMD is described in section 3. The experimental setup is elaborated in section 4. The results are presented in section 5 with a comprehensive discussion interpreting the results in section 6. Finally, the paper is concluded with key results and suggestions for future research in section 7.

2. State of the art

Process parameters for LMD play a vital role in welding process. Although there are multiple parameters involved in LMD process, Fatoba et al. [12] emphasize the significance of optimizing combination of laser power and scan speed so as to attain better results. It is found that even trivial imbalance in process parameters influence with greater impact on the end results. Likewise, Mehrabi et al. [13] and Mahamood [14] investigate effects of laser power, scanning speed, and its combination on surface finish with LMD. Results show that surface roughness is directly proportional to laser power and inversely proportional to the laser scanning speed. Maffia et al. [11] study significance of scan speed and laser power on temperature and molten pool area while employing LMD. Ghasempour-Mouziraji et al. [15] review processing parameters of LMD such as laser power, scanning speed, powder feed rate, gas flow rate, and beam diameter for ferrous and non-ferrous material.

In the domain of additive manufacturing, several approaches have been explored to embed optical fiber inside metal. Petrie et al. [16] embed copper coated fibers inside stainless steel with ultrasonic additive manufacturing for monitoring high-temperature strain. Quantification of the differential thermal strains between the fiber and the steel substrate was included in

Fig. 1. An optical fiber cable integrated within the metal sheet [7]

this work. Continuing with same approach, Hyer et al. [17] first explored parameters on metal plate and then applied the explored parameters on complex geometries to embed copper and gold coated fibers inside stainless steel. Havermann et al. [18] improve protection by coating optical fiber with nickel through sputtering and electroplating, followed by embedding nickel coated optical fibers into stainless steel using selective laser melting technology. Later, Havermann et al. [19] demonstrate in-situ strain and temperature measurements from fibers, incorporated in U-shaped groves, applicable in harsh environments.

Kim et al. [20] embed nickel coated fiber optic sensor inside stainless steel via LMD and examine the heat impact on fibers by varying the thickness of nickel jacket. Line-by-line printing and stop process is applied and feasibility for monitoring high temperature is demonstrated. Similarly, Zou et al. [21] embed nickel coated single-mode fibers inside metal with LMD for temperature and residual strain measurement. Grandal et al. [22] embed nickel and copper coated fiber Bragg grating sensor in tin alloy through wire-based LMD and investigate losses in the optics before and after the LMD process at different powers.

Several shielding methods are put into practice to minimize heat impact of LMD. Petrat et al. [23] embed electronic with LMD into an additive manufactured metal component. Nickel wire is sheathed with fiberglass that can withstand temperature up to 900 °C for few seconds.

Fig. 2. Illustration of the experiment performed by Manns et al. [7]

Fig. 3. Illustration of experiment (a) front view; (b) top view

Additionally, 10 seconds pause is introduced after printing each track in order to minimize the heat impact. Ceramics have high melting points and low thermal conductivity, thus ideal for surface protection [24]. Feldhausen et al. [25] mark usage of ceramic as protection from heat while integrating strain and temperature sensors. Ceramic is placed on metal substrate in prior to deposit metal powder with LMD. Likewise, Werkle et al. [26] applies insulating layer of ceramic compound on iron specimens and weld copper alloy on top with LMD.

Manns et al. [7] perform principle test to embed single-mode optical fiber inside sheet metal with LMD near functional surface (see Fig. 1). A method is proposed to weld optical fiber cable inside metal by employing ceramic sleeve for shielding the cable. Additionally, metallic strip further protects the ceramic sheathed cable from direct exposure to laser. The design illustration of experiment is depicted in Fig. 2. As a result of weld with 1000 W power, the surface quality is compromised and pores are visible on the roof wall. Also, black burn marks on substrate are visible that might be due to excessive heat. However, the results are promising since light propagation capability of fiber is preserved. Nevertheless, it is necessary to optimize LMD process parameters in order to ensure improved results.

3. Methodology

3.1. Optimization of parameters

Two different types of metal sheet are selected. One type of metal sheet serves as a substrate on which optical fiber has to be embedded. Other metal sheet acts as a weld pool layer for fiber. Several parameter settings are tested on both the sheet metals. The tests are visually analyzed and optimized parameters are identified for both the sheet metals. One factor at a time approach is selected for parameter identification. For structural steel sheet, laser power is decremented with a step

size of 50 W, starting with 1000 W. Later, the spot diameter is modified with step size of 0.1 mm, keeping the laser power constant at 500 W. Similar experiment is performed for stainless steel metal sheet, maintaining the laser power 90 W. The heat impact of weld pool is analyzed by visualizing the bottom side of the weld pool and evaluating the burn marks.

3.2. Embedding optical fiber with optimized parameters

Foremost, the two metal sheets, (i) in which optical fiber is to be embedded, and (ii) which is to be placed on top of fiber, are laser cut. A rectangular groove is milled in the center of substrate metal sheet for placing fiber optic cable. Fiber optic cable with plastic jacket is encased in a ceramic sleeve so as to protect it from melting.

Side walls are fabricated on substrate metal sheet on both sides of the groove resulting a cavity. A single layer is printed with optimized parameters and a scan speed of 0.30 m/min. Each side wall is composed of three layers stacked one by one on metal sheet. Fiber optic cable, sheathed with ceramic sleeve, is placed inside the cavity. A rectangular metal strip is placed on the top of fiber optic cable covering the entire cable to be embedded. A single layer is printed with optimized parameters and a scan speed of 0.20 m/min. In total twelve layers are deposited on the top, side by side and one by one. Waiting time of 250 seconds is introduced after each layer so as to minimize the heat effects. The experiment design is illustrated in Fig. 3.

3.3. Microcomputed tomography of embedded fiber

To examine heat impact of LMD on fiber, the welded fiber is first ejected from the metal and then X-rayed for performing microcomputed tomography (Micro-CT).

Fig. 4. (a) Fiber optic cable welded beneath functional surface with optimized parameters; (b) light propagating from fiber optic cable

4. Experimental Setup

The approach is experimented with a Trumpf TruLaser Cell 3000, Trumpf Laser TruDisk 4001 and multijet process nozzle SO16. The 2mm nozzle maintains 16 mm height from the substrate. Helium and Argon is employed as nozzle gas and carrier gas respectively. Martensitic high chromium stainless steel metal powder, Metco 42C by Oerlikon, is used for deposition. Chemical composition of metal powder is summarized in Table 1. For experiment, 3 mm thick structural steel sheet metal S235JRC (1.0122) is utilized as a substrate and 1 mm stainless steel sheet metal SS316L is employed as metal strip placed on top of optical fiber cable. Single mode fiber G.657.A2, sheathed with ceramic fibers' sleeves (Item no. 080-0500, 4AS.044, Final Advanced Materials GmbH) is put into operation since it is capable to withhold maximum continuous temperature of 1100 °C.

Table 1. Chemical composition of metal powder

	C	Cr	Fe	Mn	Ni	P	S	Si
%	0.18	16.22	80.91	0.06	1.59	0.006	0.012	0.70

The experiments for identifying suitable parameters are conducted on metal sheet without the fibers. Later, fiber optic cable is concealed inside metal through LMD with optimized parameters (see Fig. 4(a)). The functionality of fiber is tested with LogiLink fiber optic visual fault locator. For detailed analysis, micro-CT scans are carried out with Zeiss Xradia 610 Versa. In total, 1601 projections are captured with 7 seconds exposure time, 0.4x objective and 3 watts X-Ray power in approximately 4 hours, achieving pixel size of 3.9386 μm . The scanned results are visualized and analyzed with Dragonfly software.

5. Result

Optimized process parameters for embedding optical fiber inside sheet metal with LMD are identified. The suitable parameters identified for both the metal sheets are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. LMD process parameters

	S235JRC	SS316L
Laser power (W)	500	90
Laser spot diameter (mm)	2	1.28
Surface power density (W/mm^2)	207	72
Scan speed (m/min)	0.30	0.20
Nozzle gas flow (L/min)	10	10
Carrier gas flow (L/min)	10	10
Powder feed rate (g/min)	10	10

After applying the optimized LMD parameters, the fiber optic cable preserves its radiance property after being encased inside the metal (see Fig. 4(b)). The dimensions of substrate are 200 mm by 50 mm and the groove dimensions are 5 mm by 50 mm with depth of 1.5 mm. The metallic strip is 3.5 mm by 35 mm. Height of the welded surface from substrate achieved after LMD is 4 mm and the final width is 7 mm. Length of welded surface is 35 mm (see Fig. 3). The side walls are rather smooth however the top surface may need some post processing for finish. Neither any pore nor any damage is visible on the roof top. No bubbles are formed on the fusion surface of substrate during powder deposition. There are pale brown burn marks visible on ceramic sleeve when extracted from the deposited metal (see Fig. 5). However, the overall cable and ceramic sleeve is undamaged. Metallic strip on roof top is deformed with approximately 1° after LMD.

The Micro-CT image (see Fig. 6) gives more insight to examine the heat impact of LMD on optical fibers sheathed with ceramic sleeves. The optical fiber is enclosed with inner

Fig. 5. Pale brown marks on ceramic sleeve

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 6. Microcomputed tomographic image of fiber optic cable with ceramic sleeve (a) before embedding; (b) after embedding with unoptimized parameters [7]; (c) after embedding with optimized parameters

particles show the metallic powder. Area marked in triangle show severe thermal degradation of outer plastic sleeve from inside. Similar deformation is visible on inner plastic sleeve near the optical fiber outer layer.

The outcomes of welding optical fiber with optimized LMD parameters are portrayed in Fig. 6(c). The outer plastic sleeve is slightly deformed after the weld process only at outer circumference, as marked in rectangle. The sparkled white particles confirm presence of metal powder inside the ceramic sleeve.

6. Discussion

Results affirm that process parameters for structural and stainless steel are optimized, pertinent for welding optical fiber directly beneath sheet metal surfaces. It is observed that minimum surface power density (SPD) for structural steel and stainless steel is 207 W/mm^2 and 72 W/mm^2 respectively. SPD less than that affects fusion of powder particles with respective substrate. On the other hand, increasing the SPD introduce cracks, porosity and bubbles. Existing SPD is achieved while keeping the laser power low, since laser power directly influences heat.

The scan speed of 0.30 m/min and 0.20 m/min is selected for structural steel and stainless steel respectively. It is observed that lowering the respective scan speed for both the sheet metals create greater heat affected zone (HAZ) that in result show deeper burn marks on the other side of substrate. On the contrary, increase in the scan speed of LMD process form gaps within the deposited beads, attributed to a reduced energy dwell time per unit area, resulting in inadequate material melting and deposition, thus compromising the continuity and integrity of the deposited structure. The selected scan speed produces optimized results. The powder feed rate, carrier gas flow and nozzle gas flow are kept constant and same for both the substrate materials. An inter-layer delay is however needed to facilitate effective cooling and heat dissipation between successive layers and minimizing heat impact on embedded cable.

The metallic strip placed on the top of optical fiber is slightly distorted. It is due to the fact that optimized parameters for stainless steel were tested on metal sheet and same parameters are assumed for smaller size of strip as well. In order to avoid distortion, parameters must be optimized on strip instead of sheet. Nevertheless, the metallic strip prevents direct exposure of optical cable to the laser. The metallic strip is closely bonded with fiber optic cable encased in a ceramic sleeve. There are gaps on the four corner sides of the cable due to quadrilateral groove and non-bended metallic strip.

Since the laser power is significantly reduced, consequently heat is reduced, therefore no black burn marks are visible on the substrate that could have formed due to formation of oxide layer on surface. Increasing the flow of carrier gas to 10 L/min also aided in minimizing oxidation and effective fusion of powder on substrate.

The metal powder is able to breach the ceramic sleeve. This breach could be a result of open side patches in between metallic strip and the side walls. Also, it could be due to the space that might have formed due to deformation of metallic

and outer plastic sleeve. In between two plastic layer exists an unknown material. The outermost dotted layer is ceramic sleeve, as shown in Fig. 6(a). Results of micro-CT scans from previous work [7] are portrayed in Fig. 6(b). The glistened

strip. However, by lowering laser power to 90 W, less heat exposure is assumed, resulting in less thermal degradation of plastic sleeve.

Light propagation through the fiber optic cable confirms its intactness. However, attenuation of light and change in wavelength remains unexplored, that might have occurred due to excessive heat after LMD process. Sensitivity of welded optical fiber to temperature and strain is also not yet explored in this experiment.

In comparison to the previous work cf. [7], the process parameters of LMD are optimized. Overall, the optimized parameters significantly decreased the heat impact of LMD on fibers and produced improved surface finish on metal sheets. This method and process parameter is tested to weld silica-based optical fiber with LMD. The tests may also be extended to other types of optical fiber and optical sensors in order to measure physical quantities like temperature and strain near functional surface.

7. Conclusion and Outlook

This novel work foster collaboration between sensors and manufacturing research community. The key findings contribute to the existing knowledge base and provide basis for future researchers to implant fiber optic-based sensors inside metal closed to functional surfaces and tools for improved manufacturing with smart sensing capabilities. By applying the optimized LMD parameters, the fiber can be conserved and its functionality can be maintained. Parameters maintaining low temperatures for lesser heat impact on fibers while producing quality surfaces are yet to explore. Also, detailed study to understand the effects of LMD on the optical characteristics of fiber is proposed for the future prospects. Later, tests are proposed to measure sensitivity of optical fibers after LMD for measuring temperature and strain.

Acknowledgements

This research has been funded by the Horizon Europe FLEX4RES project with Grant Agreement Number 101091903.

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